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EVALUATION OF THERMAL PROPERTIES OF E-GLASS/ EPOXY COMPOSITES FILLED BY DIFFERENT FILLER MATERIALS

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Abstract

Composites are engineered or naturally occurring materials made out of two or more constituents. To obtain the better properties of composites material its individual constituents are modified. A composites material is difficult to carry out due to the anisotropic and non-homogeneous structure of composites and to the high abrasiveness of their reinforcing constituents. In this present work of the mechanical and thermal properties of E-glass/Epoxy composite materials with fillers (Al_2O_3 and SiO_2) has pointed to investigate the materials added to the matrix help amending the mechanically operating properties and thermally affected of a composite. The results of various characterization tests are reported here. This includes evaluation of tensile strength, torsion test, hardness test, thermal conductivity, thermal expansion coefficient measurement, fire resistance test and flame propagation rate has been experimentally recorded. As per the experimental results, this present work conclude that if we mixing 20% of Al_2O_3 or SiO_2 with 50% of fiber and 30% of resins to make a composite material then we can easily see the SiO_2 have a greater mechanical properties than Al_2O_3 , so this present work proposed to SiO_2 instead Al_2O_3 where the greater strength needed. It also observed that composites filled by (20% Vol) Al_2O_3 and (25% Vol) SiO_2 exhibited low thermal conductivity it may be due to that while heating of materials slow chemical reaction takes place in Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 and releases the small amount of water and this released water resist the heat flow and seems possible that there is a fundamental difficult in transferring heat from the matrix to the fibers. Increase the addition of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 to composites reduces the thermal expansion coefficient. It has been noticed that (25% Vol) Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 filled composite exhibited less thermal expansion coefficient this may be by adding the more fillers in composite materials providing good filler matrix interaction in the system, the filler binds the matrix and prevents it from expanding as much as it would on its own. The flammability of composites is reduces when addition of thermally active fillers like oxides to the polymer matrix is

tried. From the results it is observed that increase the loading of SiO₂ increase the time to ignition and reduces the flame propagation rate because Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ is active in both the condensed and gas phases of the combustion process and it is remarkably effective in suppressing flaming combustion and smoke.

Keywords: Thermal Properties, E-Glass/Epoxy, Composite Materials

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites are engineered or naturally occurring materials made out of two or more components. To obtain the better properties of composites material its individual constituents are modified. Generally in composites, there are two phases; continual phase is called matrix and the reinforcing phase is called fibre. [1]. The function of matrix is to transfer external load, to hold the fibre and to protect fibre from external environment. In addition, it also carries transverse load and inter-laminar shear stress. [2]. Similarly, the role of fibre is to increase Young's modulus of composites.

Composites are made by combining two or more materials with different properties to get their useful properties and reduce their weaknesses. In general, the properties of composite materials are superior in many respects, to those of the individual constituents [3].

This has provided the main motivation for the research and development of composite materials. The composite materials have advantage over other conventional materials due to their higher specific properties such as tensile, impact and flexural strengths, stiffness and fatigue characteristics, which enable structural design to be more versatile.

Thermal conductivity is the ability of material to conduct heat through it. On the other hand, thermal resistivity is reciprocal of thermal conductivity. Each material has its own thermal behaviour.

The theory of thermal conductivity was proposed by Fourier in 1822. According to Fourier, the fundamental heat conduction equation can be stated as "For a homogeneous solid, the local heat flux is proportional to the negative local temperature gradient". [11]

2. MATERIALS USED

This chapter describes the details of processing of the composites and the experimental procedures followed for their characterization and behaviour evaluation. The raw materials used in this work are:

1. E-glass Fibre (Glass 50%)
2. Epoxy Resin (Polyester 25% to 30%)
3. Aluminum Oxide (Al₂O₃)
4. Silica Oxide (SiO₂)

3. MANUFACTURING METHOD

There are many different lamination techniques available. Several automated and semi-automated fabrication techniques have been developed to eliminate variability in hand lamination and to prolong production runs. The semi-automated methods are based on matched die moulding which permits critical control of thickness and glass content and produces a moulding with two good surfaces. Based on mould is used to laminate the composite material, there are two kinds of lamination process. They are open mould process and closed mould process.

In this investigation we used hand lay-up process which is open moulding method to manufacturing the composites product which has a wide variety of products including: boats, tanks, housing for auto components and many other products. First of all gel coat is applied in the moulding surface. Then after roll stock glass fibre are placed when the gel coat has cured. The laminating resin is applied by pouring, brushing, spraying, or using a paint roller. Paint rollers or squeegees are used to consolidate the laminate, thoroughly wetting the reinforcement, and removing entrapped air. Low density core materials are also added sometime when it is necessary.

Figure 1: Hand Lay-Up Process

4. COMPOSITIONS FOR THE SPECIMEN

So compositions of the composites materials are as follows

- 50% Resin + 50% Fibre
- 30% Resin + 20%Al₂O₃+50% Fibre
- 25% Resin + 25%Al₂O₃+50% Fibre
- 30% Resin + 20%SiO₂+50% Fibre
- 25% Resin + 25%SiO₂+50% Fibre

5. MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF COMPOSITIES

Hand lay-up molding is used for the production of parts of any dimensions such as technical parts with a surface area of a few square feet, as well as swimming pools as large as 1600 square feet (approx. 150 m²). But this method is generally limited to the manufacture of parts with relatively simple shapes that require only one face to have a smooth appearance (the other face being rough from the molding operation). It is recommended for small and medium volumes requiring minimal investment in molds and equipment.

The contact molding method consists of applying these elements successively onto a mold surface:

- A Release Agent,
- A Gel Coat,
- A layer of liquid thermosetting Resin, of viscosity between 0.3 and 0.4 Pa-s, and of medium reactivity,
- A layer of reinforcement (glass, aramid, carbon, etc.) in the form of chopped strand Mat or woven Roving Impregnation of the reinforcement is done by hand using a roller or a brush.

This operation is repeated for each layer of reinforcement in order to obtain the desired Thickness of the structure.

6. ORIENTATION OF FIBER

- Fibre orientation in sheet form 0-90.
- Fibre used- Chopped Slandered Mat (CSM)/E-Glass.
- Fibre orientation in cylindrical rod is random.
- Fibre used- Glass Roving

7. DIMENSIONS OF THE SPECIMENS

- Dimensions of specimen for tensile test are 250 mm x 65 mm X 5 mm
- Dimensions of specimen for torsion test are Length = 200 mm and Diameter = 20 mm
- Dimensions of specimen for Vickers Hardness Test is 85 mm x 25 mm X 5 mm

8. EXPERIMENTAL SETUPS

8.1 Mechanical Property test

This section includes experimental setups of Tensile Testing Machine, Torsion Testing Machine and Vickers Hardness Testing Machine for their results and observations.

8.2 Thermal Property test

Thermal conductivity and thermal expansion coefficient of prepared composites was determined according to standard methods.

8.2.1 Thermal Conductivity

Thermal conductivity measurements are carried out under steady state condition. According to ASTM E1530 disc shaped specimens with diameter of 50mm and thickness of 10mm are used in the instrument for thermal conductivity measurements. A known constant heat is applied from one side of the specimen. When the thermal equilibrium is attained and the system approaches to steady state situation, the temperature of top bottom surfaces were measured by using thermocouples installed on top and bottom of the specimen. Knowing the values of heat supplied, temperatures, and thickness, the thermal conductivity was determined by employing one-dimensional Fourier's law of conduction. All measurements are carried out approximately in the similar temperature range, i.e., 25-90 oC

$$Q = -KA \frac{dT}{dx} = (KA (T_1 - T_2))/L \quad (1)$$

Where

Q= Heat transfer rate (W)

K= Thermal conductivity (W/m °C)

A=Area (m²)

T1= temperature at bottom surface of the sample (°C)

T2= Temperature at top surface of the sample (°C)

L= Thickness of the sample

dT/dx = Temperature gradient

8.2.2 Thermal Expansion Coefficient Measurement

The specimens for the thermal expansion coefficient testing had length and thickness 90mm and 10mm respectively. The linear thermal expansion tests are performed over the temperature range of 25 to 90oC using electric furnace. The samples are slowly heated from 30 to 90 OC in the electric furnace and kept at 90OC for 10 min. Thermal Expansion Coefficient is then given by the relationship

$$\alpha = \Delta L / L \Delta T \quad (2)$$

Where

α = Thermal Expansion coefficient

L = Original length of the sample

ΔL = Change in length of the sample

ΔT = Temperature change

8.2.3 Fire Resistance Test

The fire properties of composite materials depend on several factors: the type of material, the fire conditions, and the test method used to measure the property.

Time to ignition is the period of time that a combustible material can with stand exposure to a constant heat flux before igniting and undergoing sustained flaming combustion, more simply, it is the time taken for a material to start burning. The ignition time can be used as a rough measure of the flammability resistance of material. Obviously it is desirable to use material with long ignition times in high fire risk applications. Extending the time- to- ignition value reduces the fire hazard of composite material used in an aircraft. The unit of time-to-ignition is seconds (Sec).

Flame Propagation Rate: The rate of the movement of the flame front is defined as the flame propagation rate.

9. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This work presents the mechanical properties and thermal properties of the E-glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . Fillers prepared for this present investigation. Details of processing of these composites and the tests conducted on them have been described in the previous section.

The results of various characterization tests are reported here. This includes evaluation of tensile strength, torsion test, hardness test, thermal conductivity, thermal expansion coefficient measurement, fire resistance test and flame propagation rate has been studied and discussed. The interpretation of the results and the comparison among various composite specimens are following:

9.1 Mechanical Characteristics

9.1.1 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites without filler (Resin and Fiber):

- a. Tensile Strength from Tensile Test is 20700 N
- b. Torsion Strength from Torsion Test is 10.2 N.m
- c. Hardness from Vickers Testing Machine is 42 HV

9.1.2 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with filler Al_2O_3 :

- a. Tensile Strength from Tensile Test is 22145 N
- b. Torsion Strength from Torsion Test is 5.10 N.m
- c. Hardness from Vickers Testing Machine is 63.4 HV

9.1.3 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with filler SiO_2 :

- a. Tensile Strength from Tensile Test is 21442 N
- b. Torsion Strength from Torsion Test is 33.45 N.m
- c. Hardness from Vickers Testing Machine is 72.22 HV

As per the above experimental results, this present work conclude that if we mix 20% of Al_2O_3 or SiO_2 with fiber and resins to make a composite material then we can easily see the SiO_2 have a greater mechanical properties than Al_2O_3 , so this present work proposed to SiO_2 instead Al_2O_3 where the greater strength needed.

9.2 Thermal Characteristics

9.2.1 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites without filler (Resin and Fiber):

- a. Thermal Conductivity is 3.2 W/m°C
- b. Thermal Expansion Coefficient is 1.99×10^{-5} /°C
- c. Time to Ignition in 09 Second
- d. Flame Propagation Rate is 0.65 mm/second

9.2.2 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with filler 20 % Al_2O_3 :

- a. Thermal Conductivity is 1.48 W/m°C
- b. Thermal Expansion Coefficient is 2.66×10^{-5} /°C
- c. Time to Ignition in 12 Second
- d. Flame Propagation Rate is 0.55 mm/second

9.2.3 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with filler 25 % Al_2O_3 :

- a. Thermal Conductivity is 1.91 W/m°C
- b. Thermal Expansion Coefficient is 2.10×10^{-5} /°C
- c. Time to Ignition in 16 Second
- d. Flame Propagation Rate is 0.49 mm/second

9.2.4 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with filler 20 % SiO₂:

- a. Thermal Conductivity is 1.52 W/m°C
- b. Thermal Expansion Coefficient is 2.45×10^{-5} /°C
- c. Time to Ignition in 9 Second
- d. Flame Propagation Rate is 0.32 mm/second

9.2.5 E-Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites with filler 25 % SiO₂:

- a. Thermal Conductivity is 1.16 W/m°C
- b. Thermal Expansion Coefficient is 2.02×10^{-5} /°C
- c. Time to Ignition in 8 Second
- d. Flame Propagation Rate is 0.29 mm/second

As per the above experimental results, this present work conclude the following

1. Thermal conductivity: From the obtained results it is observed that composites filled by (20% Vol) Al₂O₃ and (25% Vol) SiO₂ exhibited low thermal conductivity it may be due to that while heating of materials slow chemical reaction takes place in Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ and releases the small amount of water and this released water resist the heat flow and seems possible that there is a fundamental difficult in transferring heat from the matrix to the fibers.

2. Thermal Expansion Coefficient: From the experimental results it is observed that increase the addition of Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ to composites reduces the thermal expansion coefficient. It has been noticed that (25% Vol) Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ filled composite exhibited less thermal expansion coefficient this may be by adding the more fillers in composite materials providing good filler matrix interaction in the system, the filler binds the matrix and prevents it from expanding as much as it would on its own. Subsequently, this would affect the thermal expansion of the composite system. The many studies have shown that materials with higher filler content leads to a lower thermal expansion coefficient.

3. Time to Ignition and Flame Propagation Rate: The flammability of composites is reduces when addition of thermally active fillers like oxides to the polymer matrix is tried. From the results it is observed that increase the loading of SiO₂ increase the time to ignition and reduces the flame propagation rate because Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ is active in both the condensed and gas phases of the combustion process and it is remarkably effective in suppressing flaming combustion and smoke. The main condensed phase mechanism of alumina oxide and silica oxide is the absorption of heat when the filler decomposes.

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